

Conference Abstract

Conservation significance and habitats variety in the Western Rhodope Mts. as a factor for the diversity of the ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae)

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Abstract

This study concerns the Western Rhodope Mts. (Southern Bulgaria), the conservationally significant habitats and the carabid beetles occurring in them. All sixty-seven habitats are systematized according to their EUNIS level and type and conservation status, and the threats to the important carabid species are assessed. The association of the carabids with specific habitats and the attachment to particular environmental conditions are discussed. Carabids with conservational value are discussed and a list of the protected (four) and endemic (thirty-nine) species is given. The anthropogenic impacts in the area were also assessed. The main threats and problems related to the degradation and destruction of natural habitats and, hence, decreases to the conservation significance of the area, were established and systematised in eight categories, and measures for minimizing these negative impacts are proposed.

Keywords

carabids, conservation, natural habitats, Western Rhodopes

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